

Sample Name: PP <1 μm

Material: Polypropylene

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 89% particles are <1 μm
- Particles have an irregular rounded morphology
- $8.0 \pm 4.0 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- 16400 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- Sample contains 16 wt% talc determined by XRF and 42% determined by TGA
 - Lower value through XRF due to unsuitability of XRF for determining polymer composition
 - TGA value of 42% higher than manufacturer's specification of 30% suggesting this fraction may also contain loose talc particles released during milling
- Cl, P, Ca and Fe were the most abundant contaminants, all <1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
 - Ca, Zn and P are present in the stabilisers
 - Fe, Ni, Cr are present due to stainless steel
 - Zr and Y are present due to the milling beads
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PP spectrum with no evidence of degradation, lower intensity is due to particle size

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_V : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_N : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D _v	D _N	N _w	A _w
8.10±0.60	3.27±0.26	1.18±0.21	0.59±0.11	5.83±0.16	0.40±0.08	8.0±4.0 10 ¹¹	16400±920

Morphology (using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Component	Concentration
C ₃ H ₆ (PP)	83.6%
Mg ₃ Si ₄ O ₁₀ (OH) ₂ (Talc)*	16.2%
Cl	635 μg/g
P	425 μg/g
Ca	375 μg/g
Fe	329 μg/g
Ti	21 μg/g
Cr	13 μg/g
Zr	5 μg/g
Ni	5 μg/g
Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn	<2 μg/g

*Quantification calculated based on oxide structure, Mg and Si concentrations

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)